
Deliverable D-WP6.1 – User manual for construction and implementation of One Health dashboards using open source tools (source codes)

OHEJP JIP MATRIX – WP6

Responsible Partner: 41-SVA, 32-FHI/NIPH
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34-PIWET, 40-FoHM, 45-RUOKA,
36-INSA

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Title OHEJP deliverable	D-WP6.1 – User manual for construction and implementation of One Health dashboards using open source tools (source codes)		
WP and task	WP6-T2 – Defining the content needs for cross-sectoral decision and collaboration dashboards		
Leader	41-SVA, 32-FHI/NIPH		
Other contributors	1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 21-APHA, 28-IZSAM, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET, 40-FoHM, 45-RUOKA, 36-INSA		
Due month of the deliverable	M58		
Actual submission month	M58		
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R, DEC Save date: 31-Oct-22		
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	PU <i>See updated Grant Agreement</i>		
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 2 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/>
	OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 5 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 6 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/>	Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/>	
	National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/>		
	EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EEA <input type="checkbox"/>
	EMA <input type="checkbox"/>	FAO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	WHO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	OIE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
	Other international stakeholder(s): as per OHEJP dissemination plans		
	Social Media: n.a.		
	Other recipient(s): n.a.		

D-WP6.1: THE DASHBOARD INFORMATION CENTRE

User manual for construction and implementation of OH dashboards using open source tools (source codes)

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Abbreviations

AH:	Animal Health
CSS:	Cascading Style Sheets
DIC:	Dashboard Information Centre
FS:	Food Safety
HTML:	Hypertext Markup Language
IT:	Information Technology
JS:	JavaScript
OH:	One Health
OHEJP:	One Health European Joint Programme
OHS:	One Health Surveillance
PH:	Public Health
SOP:	Standard Operating Procedure
UI:	User Interface
UX:	User Experience
WP:	Work Package

Introduction

One Health Surveillance (OHS) refers to the combination of health surveillance data and knowledge from the three health sectors — public health (PH), animal health (AH) and food safety (FS) — in order to understand how the health of humans, animals and the environment are connected and affect each other.

MATRIX is a project of the [One Health European Joint Programme \(OHEJP\)](#), a partnership of 44 food, veterinary and medical laboratories and institutes across Europe and the [Med-Vet-Net Association](#). MATRIX connects existing cross-sectorial One Health programmes in European countries. Today, 19 partner institutes representing the AH, PH and FS sectors from 12 countries continue a collaboration that started early in 2020 and will end in December 2022. More information can be found [here](#).

The purpose of MATRIX is to create practical solutions for European countries to support and to advance the implementation of OHS. MATRIX invites European institutes working in the AH, PH and FS sectors to consider the opportunity to adopt these solutions and to further build upon them.

Work Package (WP) 6 focuses on visualisation of OHS inputs and outputs for the use of surveillance officials in PH, AH and FS. This is achieved through the creation of dashboards, which include surveillance data from all three sectors.

A dashboard is a form of graphical user interface which displays data and metrics in a way that facilitates tracking, analysis and monitoring to inform decision-making. A disease surveillance dashboard might contain charts, tables, maps or other elements providing a comprehensive overview of the development of the disease in question, or even predicting future outbreak events.

The ORION project identified data sources that are already public or shared across sectors. The NOVA project built automated routines for data analyses and visualisation when trend monitoring is possible. The MATRIX project builds on these results and the experience gained through the dashboard development work to create the Dashboard Information Centre (DIC), an online resource which will serve as a manual and best-practice guide for the development of OHS dashboards. The DIC will document important aspects such as:

- Information context and end-user considerations: what information does a user or a surveillance official need on their everyday work, and in case of emergency? What kind of data can provide that information?
- Step by step guide for developing dashboards

- Possible pitfalls and biases when One Health data is co-analysed
- Example of an open-source technical solution based on the data, available resources and desired outcomes
- Contact information for experts within MATRIX with knowledge in relevant topics

This DIC will also function as an inventory and showcase of all planned, ongoing and finished dashboard activities within the participants in MATRIX, so that the provided information can be exemplified by real-world implementations.

The DIC can be found online at <https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/>.

In this deliverable we will describe the contents of the DIC, as well as the methods used to develop it and how the information behind it was collected.

Dashboard Information Centre Infrastructure

The DIC is hosted in an open repository on GitHub (<https://github.com/sva-se/matrix-dashboards>). The textual content of the site is written in the plain-text [Markdown](#) language; this makes it highly readable in source-code form which facilitates collaboration. We used the [Jekyll](#) system combined with the [Just the Docs](#) theme to transform this plain-text into a visually appealing, easy to navigate static website. The site is hosted by [GitHub Pages](#), a service which is included with every GitHub repository. This way, the website is automatically updated every time a change is pushed to the repository.

GitHub was selected as a hosting platform because of its popularity, ease-of-use and stability. The stability of the platform ensures that the DIC remains up-and-running independently, while the ease-of-use allows it to be expanded and improved in the future – by the original developers or by someone new.

Dashboard Information Centre Content

The information contained in the DIC was produced in various ways. Some of the content was produced based on group discussions, brainstorming and talks with all the participating institutes in this WP throughout the project period. Other information is based on reviewing previous experiences from former projects, talking to the people in these projects and reading literature. We also invited partners for inter-agency discussions on the opportunities and problems that can be addressed with joint analyses and/or visualisation of data regarding the hazards of relevance to MATRIX. The participants were also invited to have discussions while developing dashboards, or to reach out to other groups in their institute that have developed dashboards and would be willing to contribute with information and knowledge. Furthermore, throughout the project we have been hosting monthly meetings for which members have been encouraged to suggest topics to discuss or present, which have been a fruitful source of knowledge for building the DIC.

We have described the topics covered by the DIC below.

1. Step-by-Step Guide to Building an OHS Dashboard

In the DIC: <https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/docs/step-by-step/>

So you want to build a dashboard? Where to begin? This guide aims to answer that question and help the developer through the process of developing a dashboard for OHS. Some sections of the guide will refer to other sections of the DIC for practical examples and further reading.

To achieve an optimal result, there are certain factors that need to be addressed in the various phases of the dashboard development process. These can be divided into three stages: 1) planning the dashboard, 2) constructing the dashboard, and 3) dashboard maintenance and outreach.

1.1. Planning the Dashboard

In the planning phase, there are two aspects which need to be considered: the aim of the dashboard, and its intended user groups. These are closely linked together and will determine what kind of dashboard should be developed.

1.1.1. Aim of the Dashboard

The first question to ask is “why do we need a dashboard?” The aim of the dashboard and the issue which that aim is intended to address, should be as clear and specific as possible. This affects the rest of the development process, including data customisation, dashboard layout and which information to present.

1.1.2. User Groups

Identifying the target groups that will use the dashboard is equally, if not more, important. Together with the aim, this informs which type of content to display in the dashboard so that it becomes an interesting and relevant tool for the user groups, while also being targeted to their level of expertise on the subject. A dashboard for the general public will look different from one intended to be used by topic experts, even if the underlying data is the same.

There are three interest groups involved in the planning of a dashboard: those who develop it, those who requested it, and those who will use it. While these groups could be the same, that is not necessarily the case. Therefore it is important to understand the relationship between these interests as they should all be represented in the planning and development of the dashboard.

Once the target user groups have been identified, it is important to pinpoint their needs and how the dashboard can help them fulfil those – which also ties into the aim of the dashboard. The best way to go about this is not to think “what information would the user want?” and attempt to guess what kind of dashboard would achieve that, but rather ask “who is my user? What do they do and what do they need?” Spending time on getting to know the user in the planning phase will result in a more organic development process and save time for the developers. This co-conception can be achieved in variety ways depending on who the user groups are, including but not limited to surveys, interviews, or establishing a dashboard reference group with representatives from the users, developers and those who requested the dashboard (see more on reference groups below). The latter is especially useful if the dashboard is intended to be used by a specific group (e.g., disease or health experts) but may not be applicable if the target user group is a wider audience, such as the general public.

1.2. Developing the Dashboard

A dashboard consists of two components: the collection and processing of data (backend), and the visual representation of that data in an interactive website (frontend). Depending on the situation, the available data and the backend system for delivery of that data may or may not be in the control of the dashboard developers, which will influence the development of the dashboard and which information can be displayed in the frontend.

1.2.1. Backend Infrastructure and Data

If development and maintenance of the backend data system is not within the scope of the dashboard project, the developer group needs to be sure of what data are available, as well as the status of the data delivery system, before the dashboard development starts. Proceeding with the frontend development before the backend system is up and running may result in having to go back and redo previous work to adapt the graphical interface to the data system.

There is a need for an infrastructure or statistical tool that can organise, analyse and produce readily available data that can be used in the dashboard. An important aspect for this is how often the data should be updated (e.g., hourly, daily, weekly), which is often dependent on whether the update will happen manually or automatically. If done automatically, the backend system must be built to handle this, while if the updates will be done manually, it is essential to ensure that there is enough personnel to update the data regularly enough for the purposes of the dashboard. Whether or not the responsibility of the backend lies with the dashboard development team, it is necessary to ensure that the system has the technical compliance for supplying the dashboard and that it is built to maintain continuity and integrity. This can be achieved by detailing the specifications of the data system in a standard operating procedure (SOP). Creating a contingency plan to ensure data uptime and integrity in case of unexpected events is also beneficial. This plan should include routines for regular backup of data and how to restore this backup in the event of a disaster.

What data will be processed and presented in the dashboard depends both on what the user groups have determined as important to achieve the identified aims as well as what data are or will be available. A privacy and confidentiality assessment must also be made to determine what and how data can legally be used and presented, especially if the dashboard is going to be publicly available.

How to analyse data and in which form it should be presented are also important aspects, especially if multiple sources are going to be shown together. Datasets with the same age groups, geographical regions, time aggregation, etc, are often easier to combine and provide a more coherent picture for the users. In a One Health context, one usually needs to combine and co-analyse data from several sectors which may use different methodologies, definitions and ways of aggregating data. The challenge of analysing multisectoral data while avoiding potential pitfalls and biases is covered in Section 2.

1.2.2. Dashboard frontend

The most appropriate choice of a frontend platform for a particular dashboard project depends on several factors. Availability of resources has a major impact on this decision, both in terms of infrastructure (e.g., for hosting) and knowledge of the development, as well as financial resources. Third-party solutions require a paid license, a cost that needs to be weighed against potential costs for in-house development (programming manpower being the largest). Another factor to take into account is the structure and complexity of the data as well as potential legal aspects; if the data are sensitive, it may not be desirable to host them on a third-party platform. The matter of dashboard access (and who should have it) also needs to be considered – control of access on user-level is often easier to control in a locally developed and hosted dashboard, which may be better suited if it should not be made available for a wider audience. Oftentimes, locally developed and hosted dashboards offer a higher level of control of access on the user level, which may be better suited if the dashboard is not intended for a wider audience.

On the technical level, there is a multitude of options to choose between, from writing the website from scratch in HyperText Markup Language ([HTML](#)) and JavaScript ([JS](#)), to relying on proprietary third-party software such as [ArcGIS](#), [Tableau](#) or [PowerBI](#). A popular “middle ground” between these two extremes, which combines the control of “home-made” code with a lower learning threshold and third-party resource support is the [R language for statistical computing](#), along with its [Shiny](#) package for developing interactive interfaces. For a more in-depth description and instruction for how to use R and Shiny for dashboard development, see Section 4.

The visual design of the dashboard needs to take into account useability, which depends on the needs of the user groups and the aim of the dashboard. Navigation and orientation should be intuitive and contribute to the purpose of the dashboard: to display information efficiently and tell a story. It is also important that the dashboard is accessible, without barriers that prevent interaction or access for those with disabilities or technical restrictions in bandwidth and speed. This is especially important for public dashboards – it is often a legal requirement for websites produced within the public sector. For more in-depth guidance on dashboard design for useability and accessibility, see Section 3 on Design Considerations.

1.3. Maintenance, Feedback and Outreach

When the dashboard (or a first version of it) has been developed, efforts must be made to make sure that relevant target groups know about it (“spreading the word”), and that it remains up and running and relevant going forward. A dashboard is usually a “living document” which not only needs to be maintained, but also updated with time. For that purpose, it is a good idea to collect feedback from those who use it.

1.3.1. Maintenance and Sustainability

Much like for the backend, it is a good idea to have a contingency plan to ensure dashboard uptime and sustainability in the long-term. This should detail who is responsible for maintaining both the information content and the technical aspects of the dashboard. If code is developed in-house, it is important that it is properly annotated and documented to facilitate future evolution – this is useful regardless of whether the development team changes or remains the same.

The choice of a solution for development and hosting also affects the sustainability of the dashboard. While on-premises hosting may be beneficial for information security and control, it requires that resources are available to maintain the infrastructure – both today and in the future. Increased traffic to the dashboard may require larger investments to ensure a sufficient user experience, which could pose a challenge if resources are scarce. Using a third-party solution usually offers greater stability (provided that the responsible company remains in business), as well as scalability meaning that available storage capacity and bandwidth can be adapted to the traffic in real time. This also comes with a price, but may offer more flexibility than an in-house solution. As with choosing the appropriate development solution, the choice of hosting also depends on the needs of the dashboard and the resources available.

1.3.2. Feedback Collection

Receiving feedback on the data, design and user friendliness of the dashboard is a very important part of creating an optimal product that is widely used. This can be done using one or a combination of several tools, including questionnaires, site analytics tools (e.g., [Google Analytics](#), but **note** that there may be data protection restrictions regarding the use of such third-party services), meetings, and reference groups (more on that below). Another option could be embedding a feedback and questions and answers (Q&A) form into the dashboard itself. However, this needs to be designed in a non-intrusive way – actively asking the user for feedback through pop-ups or similar is likely to act as a deterrent and reduce the probability of receiving input.

1.3.3. Outreach

A dashboard is something that you want people to know about and use. It is therefore important to get in contact and spread the word about the dashboard to the user groups. This can be done through several communication channels, though a combination of these will most probably be best:

- Reference groups – spread the word through the people in the reference groups
- Email information – to stakeholders
- Conference – have a presentation or poster at a conference
- Web search – make sure that the dashboard is easy to find through online search engines
- Contact user groups and ask to hold a presentation about the dashboard

- Social media posts

It may be beneficial to involve the communications department of the institute where the dashboard is published, as they likely have better resources to handle communication, questions and outreach, and can do so through the institute's official channels. If so, the communications department should be familiar with the dashboard and how it works so they are prepared to answer questions that may come in or alternatively, who to forward them to.

1.3.4. Reference Groups

Reference groups consisting of users as well as representatives of all parts of the dashboard development (including communication) could be a very useful tool in all stages of dashboard development: planning, development, feedback and outreach. Direct communication in this form allows the development team to receive direct feedback on the dashboard, while also opening an opportunity to spread the word through the members' extended networks.

Whether or not it is a good idea to establish a reference group depends on the structure of the dashboard development as well as its aim and target user groups. If many interests are involved, it is a very efficient way to make sure everyone is heard informed regarding the status of the project. However, if the target users are a wider audience (such as the public) reference groups may not be a relevant tool to use. Regardless, it is still a good idea to involve the development team in a working group with close connections.

2. One Health Data Co-Analysis: Considerations, Pitfalls and Biases

In the DIC: <https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/docs/data/>

OHS brings together data from multiple sources and sectors (PH, AH, FS, environment) to analyse them together in a common context. In this co-analysis it is important to consider some potential pitfalls and sources of bias that could arise from the great diversity that exists in One Health data, and which should be considered when performing data analysis and presentation.

Below are some examples of aspects to consider, produced through a discussion workshop within WP6 of < on the 28th of October 2021, in which surveillance experts from a variety of countries and sectors participated. The document was also sent out to all WP partners after the meeting for approval and inclusion of more details/information.

2.1. Terminology and Definitions

The language and terminology used to describe disease surveillance activities in different sectors may differ, or the same terms may be used to describe different things. For example, a case may not be defined in the same way which will pose problems when comparing case data if the differences are unknown or unconsidered.

Awareness of potential terminological differences is important both when analysing One Health (OH) data and when presenting the results to the end user. Before analysis, consider: if there are differences, do they have operational relevance? For example, an outbreak may be defined differently in different sectors based on a difference in needs/objectives and capacities of response. Such differences may be more difficult and require more reasoning to circumvent but are nonetheless important to identify. When presenting OHS results in a website or dashboard, one way to avoid terminological misunderstandings is to include a glossary. Here, a useful tool to refer to is the [OHEJP ORION Glossary](#), in which a member of the OH community can look up terms and therefore be aware of potential differences in definitions across sectors. Building surveillance dashboards with the OHEJP Glossary in mind from the start ensures that terms are used correctly and consistently while also saving the effort of writing a glossary “from scratch”.

2.2. Methodologies

The laboratories involved in surveillance and the methodologies, practices and standards that they operate under may differ, both within and between sectors. One reason for this difference is that different sectors deal with different strains and pathogens to which laboratory practices need to adapt. Information about which laboratory methods have been used and for which strains is important for interpreting OH data and assessing whether they even can be analysed in a common context. Another issue related to laboratory methods when co-analysing OH data could be differences in the resources available for data management. Different sectors and different actors within sectors have different resources, which may have consequences in how data and metadata are stored and managed, which in turn could affect the ability to combine the data with that from other sectors.

To improve reporting of designs, implementations and methodologies that are used for description of outcomes in surveillance activities, the One Health Consensus Report Annotation Checklist was developed within the OHEJP ORION project (Lopez de Abechucu et al, 2022 ¹). This checklist proposes that reporters producing surveillance results should provide as much information as possible, such as which methods were used and how different strains and pathogens are dealt with. Following the checklist facilitates that the data produced can be compared across sectors in the long run, which is more valuable for the community.

¹ Lopez de Abechucu, E., Dórea, F., Buschhardt, T., Scaccia, N., Günther, T., Foddai, A., Dups-Bergmann, J., Filter, M., 2022. One Health Consensus Report Annotation Checklist (OH-CRAC): A cross-sector checklist to support harmonized annotation of surveillance data in reports. *Zoonoses and Public Health* 69, 606–614. <https://doi.org/10.1111/zph.12947>

2.3. Potential Routes of Disease Transmission

Exploring and understanding the underlying routes of disease transmission tells us how the data we observed came to be in the first place, which also helps inform how data should be analysed and presented. For example, if studying a zoonotic agent for which human cases have been observed, it is quite useful to be able to trace the infection backward and link the cases to their animal source, especially if the goal is to predict and prepare for future outbreaks. Finding this link can inform about factors such as geographical connections, expected time delay between cases and what data should be collected to achieve a timelier surveillance.

If transmission did not occur through direct contact, there exists some environmental route which needs to be studied. When doing so, one needs to be specific about one means by “the environment” and which potential routes that may include, to avoid searching in the dark. To make a proper risk assessment it is important to collect as much information and parameters as possible about the potential transmission routes so that they can be properly defined. However, in normal surveillance contexts there is usually a limit to what information is available. In this case there needs to be a discussion about what potential routes have not been explored due to missing data. This requires a surveillance system which is highly adaptable, especially when facing an emerging threat for which there may be little to no understanding of the routes of transmission.

2.4. Data Properties and Statistical Considerations

Data alone are not very useful if not accompanied by a description of the data's properties, also known as metadata ². This is especially important when matching and co-analysing data across sectors, as the metadata provides information about how data can be combined. For example, data sampled in different ways (e.g. random sampling vs. triggered sampling) cannot be compared directly unless there is metadata available to describe the sampling process (how and why) in a meaningful way for statistical methods. Again, some of these concepts may have different interpretation in different sectors (e.g. active vs passive sampling/surveillance). For posterity it is also valuable to document how OH data was integrated and subsequently analysed, and what assumptions that integration and analysis was based on.

2.5. Time Frame

Data collected and analysed in different contexts and for different purposes may be collected in different time frames. There may be variation in collection frequency, delay from collection to analysis or the time scale in which the data are reported (e.g. daily, workdays, weekly, monthly...). Which timeframe that is relevant to use is highly dependent on the surveillance question. This is closely related to the topic of terminology and case definitions, in that whenever the time frame used has an operational relevance one should think of ways to make different needs match.

Sometimes the issue is simply one of how time is defined, and which formats are used, something that is dependent on where in the world and in what context the data were recorded. For statistical work, it is often a problem that time data are not stored in a format that can be worked with programmatically. To circumvent this, time can be stored in the universal Unix format (number of seconds since 1 January 1970), but this requires some effort to subsequently translate it into a format that makes sense for the users.

In disease surveillance, there will always be some delay between infection, sample collection, sample analysis, reporting, data analysis and presentation of results. It is important to be aware of what delays exist and how they affect the surveillance, especially when aligning case curves from different sectors or training statistical models to predict future development.

² <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/metadata>

2.6. Geographical Scope

All geographical data needs to be aggregated to some level to be useful, and when comparing aggregated data (e.g. AH data collected on farm level vs. human case data on municipal level). If this is the case, it is necessary to think about if and how these data can be translated into a common context. Matching geographical surveillance data may be difficult depending on what kind of location metadata is available. How the data should be matched also depends on the underlying route of transmission.

Differences may not just be due to varying structures and needs of different sectors; there may also be intra-sector variation due to different possible levels of granularity. In countries with a high degree of regional autonomy, for example, data may not be collected and aggregated the same way in all regions. This becomes especially relevant in international surveillance contexts. Geographical data can also vary structurally in terms of data format (e.g. vector data vs raster data) or visualisation properties such as raster size (geographical resolution) and which coordinate systems were used. Such technical aspects are equally important to ensure that data are matched correctly.

2.7. User Group Considerations

The desired outcome of the surveillance and an associated dashboard will naturally depend on the target audience. Experts of different sectors will be interested in different perspectives, but they sometimes overlap. It is this overlap, where the results are valuable for more than one sector, which is the core of OHS. Knowledge of who will be interested in the results and what they want to see in a dashboard is therefore crucial for creating a useful product. This is not just a consideration for the design stage of dashboard development but will be vital in deciding what type data is collected and how they are analysed and presented. As such, the target audience should be defined as early as possible. For the development of dashboards, a general rule of thumb is that every piece of information presented in the dashboard should be justified from a user point of view, which means that one must define what use is expected by the audience and whether that information meets the expectation.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, it has become evident that there could be a great interest in surveillance data outside the realms of expert authorities and academia, to the public as well as companies, statistical institutes, etc. This comes with great technical requirements on the surveillance institutes, which poses challenges if the information technology (IT) infrastructure is not prepared for a wide audience. The pandemic has also created a great demand for real-time surveillance data where the results are expected to be available as soon as possible, which brings its own technical challenges but also risks causing confusion as numbers and figures will need to be adjusted a posteriori as new data keep coming in. All in all, the pandemic has clearly shown that when working with disease surveillance with an interest for the wider public it is important to have the infrastructure capacity to handle large amounts traffic, and to consider the timeliness with which data should be published. With the user group in mind, there needs to be a consideration of when and how often information presented in a dashboard should be updated. What is the operational relevance of updating the dashboard with a certain frequency? How real-time is real-time enough? In urgent situations it may be advantageous to prioritise timeliness, while other contexts should favour data completeness.

3. Design Considerations

In the DIC: <https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/docs/design/>

This section is meant to be a support for developers during the visual design process of the dashboard, to help develop a finished product which is visually appealing, accessible and easy to use.

Design refers here to the substantial process of both content planning and visual design. Readers of this manual who are familiar with the data that will populate the dashboard, will most likely be more concerned and more skilled in the content planning phase. For the sake of completeness, this chapter will also cover some principles of visual design and some considerations regarding dashboard design specifically. However, for all projects but especially complex projects and public-facing dashboards, it is highly recommended to enlist the help of a web designer, for example from the communication department of your institute.

This section is not meant to be exhaustive, but rather an introduction and guide to the process of dashboard design.

3.1. Content Planning

The content planning phase is crucial to create a good product that will fulfil its purpose and properly meet the needs of the user. Going through this phase meticulously will give clarity for the upcoming development, allow scalability and flexibility, and save time and resources in the long run.

The steps involved in this phase are to (1) define in detail what your product will be, (2) identify the profile of the intended user(s) and (3) design the content flow and layout of your dashboard.

3.1.1. Know Your Product

Content planning begins with clearly identifying the nature, aim, scope and limitations of your product. Please see section 1.1 for further information.

3.1.2. Know Your Users

Identifying the problems, needs and expectations of the users is the key to building a successful and useful product. It would be unwise to develop the exact same dashboard for a small set of experts and for the general public. Likewise, you, as for instance a scientist developing a dashboard, have a different level of knowledge and familiarity with the content of the dashboard than the intended user. Doing detailed user profiling will help to craft a platform fully targeted to the needs of the users.

User profiling is a process where you create a fictional user persona for each distinct group of target users (Figure 1). This set of user personas acts as a simplified representation of your user base, with characteristics, limitations, and expectations that are similar to those of your users. This concretises the plurality of the user base into a simple model of needs and limitations, which should guide the design choices and help craft a more user-friendly platform.

Figure 1. Example of a set of user persona and resulting content design choices for a project on respiratory diseases. Project A would be a dashboard open to the general public, while Project B would be restricted to a group of experts and decision-makers.

3.1.3. Layout Design

With the insight gained from product definition and user profiling, it is now possible to start organising content in a meaningful way.

3.1.3.1. Global Page Layout

In this step, you decide which basic website elements (logo, menu, footer, ...) will be present, and where to display them on the page. This will be in parts dependent on the technical solution you have chosen to develop the dashboard, and how much flexibility it allows.

In general, don't get too creative. Most people are familiar with the internet and have a set of expectations when it comes to navigating a website. Deviating from these expectations will only make your dashboard harder to use.

Basic web elements which are expected to be found include the following:

- Logo and website name – Top of the page. Centred or in the left corner

- Main navigation menu – Top of the page. Below or to the right of the logo. Alternatively in a sidebar to the left of the page.
- Main content – Occupies most of the screen. Traditionally will be linear content on a scrollable long page, with fixed width and centred on the screen. Alternatively, dashboards can be presented as tiled blocks of content on a grid that takes the whole screen.
- Footer – Optional but very useful. A band occupying the whole bottom section of a page. Usually contains:
 - Logo and name of the page
 - Copyright with date of activity and name of the developer/page owner/institute
 - Main navigation links
 - Contact information
 - Legal information, logos and links to partner institutions, links to employees only sections, etc (optional)

3.1.3.2. Content Structure

In this step you start deciding on the content (text, maps, graphs, interactive input fields, downloadable elements, ...) that your dashboard will contain, and how to structure this content. The user research done previously should greatly inform the decisions you take here.

The goal is to divide and organise the information in meaningful blocks and create a natural flow of content that guides the user to the information they need. Based on the product definition and the overview of your users' needs, you can decide which content is needed, how to structure it and in which order it should be introduced. Will you have tabs and subtabs? What graphs or visualisations will you have? Are they interactive? What text is needed to accompany the data?

Start designing at a global level and dive into details iteratively. At each step, the content should flow in a meaningful way, before you delve deeper into specifics.

3.1.3.3. Wireframing

Wireframing is a common web design tool to plan the structure of content. It is a process where one draws boxes and lines to represent content blocks. It is usually done with pen and paper. At this stage, the goal is to put ideas on paper freely, and quickly iterate over several ideas and options. There exist some wireframing softwares, but considering their learning curve and slowness of use, analogue tools will always present less of a barrier. These digital tools can be useful later on, to produce a clean version of the wireframes to share with colleagues and stakeholders (Figure 2).

Wireframing allows you to think of the nature of the content and the flow of information, without getting distracted by the wording of a text, the colours and styles of a graph, or any other details. This technique allows you to refine the flow of content and make sure that the information is properly introduced, that the most important information is given a choice location on the page, and that the user would be able to go through an action and achieve their goal in the most efficient way.

This technique should be used in the initial stage of page layout and content structuring, but can also be used later on for more detailed elements (e.g., a complex block of content with a graph, a legend, a figure caption, a user input field with a text field and dropdown menus and a final download button).

Figure 2. Example of wireframing for a dashboard on Campylobacter surveillance.

3.2. Visual Design

Visual design is deciding how the information is being presented. It is done through for instance page layout, colour palette, font choices, illustration, and graphic design. It relies on various principles such as hierarchy, contrast or repetition, which are known to influence how the eye identifies and understands

visual elements and patterns. It is a very important part of the dashboard design process. A good UI (User interface) is essential to craft a good UX (User experience) and will allow the user to reach information more efficiently.

It does require skills and knowledge that most would not be experts in. Ideally, you will have the support of an experienced designer in your team or from the Communications Department of your institute. This subsection is only aiming to give some guidelines and pointers to learn further on these topics.

Some basic qualities of a good design are that it is accessible (the information is reachable and understandable), and that it is visually pleasing (it is comfortable and/or interesting to use the platform).

3.2.1. Accessibility

When creating website, you should always make sure that your product is accessible. Accessibility requirements are extremely important (and sometimes required by law), especially for dashboards open to the public. The Communication Department of your institute will have rules and resources to make sure you are providing a platform accessible to all. These are some things to keep in mind:

- Colour palettes should be accessible to colourblind and other visually impaired people. That means having colour being contrasted enough on their background, never using a red/green dichotomy for graphs, and relying on symbols more than colours to convey information if possible.
- All important features should be keyboard accessible.
- The text and semantic of your page should be screen-reader friendly. That means using HTML tags in a semantically correct way, and always providing ALT text to images.

This is especially important if you are developing your own custom code with basic HTML/CSS/JS. But note that some dashboard-making solutions are still lagging behind on some aspects (e.g., some input fields in R shiny are not yet keyboard accessible, but upcoming versions should fix this). You need to do a concerted effort to go through all aspects of your website and make sure that you are as accessible as possible.

More information on web accessibility:

- [W3 Web Accessibility Initiative](#) - extensive resources, standards and guidelines
- [Mozilla developer's tutorials on accessibility](#) - very pedagogic and understandable learning material

3.2.2. Principles of Visual Design

Principles of visual design include tools such as emphasis, contrast, similarity, repetition, and alignment. There appears to be as many lists of these principles as there are designers, with varying numbers, nomenclature and definition. A designer uses these tools to craft a specific experience for the viewer, by putting focus on specific elements, directing the eye along a specific path, and increasing visual interest and appeal. There are many wrong ways to do it, and no single right way, which is why the input of an experienced designer will always be beneficial.

If you do not feel confident in this task, the safest option is always to keep things simple. If you have a solid content structure from the previous step, that can be good enough. Most development tools will output a product with a default basic UI which can be sufficient. Custom visual design will help creating a better product, but it is not strictly necessary.

Here are some ways these principles can be used to craft a better UI and UX:

- Hierarchy: having a good visual hierarchy between different elements will help the user understand the structure of the website better (having title, headers and subheaders with

varying degrees of emphasis), and reach the important information faster (using bold text for important sentences, but not overusing it).

- Unity or consistency: having a unified design system (a set of decisions regarding font type, font size, color, graphic style) throughout the dashboard will help the user understand the structure of the content better (e.g., important takeaway messages will be displayed in bold italic). You don't want to start introducing exceptions (e.g., an important sentence displayed in bold underline), and break the underlying patterns that the user has learned about your platform. Breaking such patterns will make it harder for the user to find and understand the information presented to them. It can be difficult to achieve if you are working collaboratively, or even alone along a longer time period. It is thus recommended to decide on a design system prior development, to avoid inconsistencies. You can also do a full redesign during development. Check the consistency in text colour and emphasis (bold/italic/underline), in spacing between paragraphs and around figures, in page structure for multi-tabs dashboards, in graph and map styles, in the vocabulary used throughout the website, etc.
- White space or negative space: creating breathing room around elements will allow the user's eye to land easier on different blocks of information and their mind to rest and refocus. It will help you show a clearer structure of content and put emphasis on what is important. You can, for example, use margins around graphs, increase the line height of text, and increase the space between paragraphs.

If you are interested, you can find more information here:

- [Short video on the Principles of Design](#)
- Simple web search for "Fundamentals of web design", "Principles of visual design" or the like.

3.2.3. Tips for Better Dashboard Design

Some miscellaneous tips to improving the UI or UX of your dashboard:

- Involve the Communications Department early in the process!
- Various UI features that will improve UX:
 - Back to top button for long linear pages
 - Spinning wheel on loading elements to show that something is happening and the user should just wait
 - Conditional feedback message based on user interaction (e.g., a success message after downloading a file)
 - Custom explicit error messages for all situations (url invalid, database failed to load, user input invalid...)
 - Breadcrumb links to help navigation in complex dashboards (e.g., One Health > Projects > MATRIX > WP6)

4. Building a Dashboard with R Shiny

In the DIC: <https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/docs/r-shiny/>

Here we provide more detailed information about R Shiny, a popular and powerful open-source technical solution for developing and hosting dashboards. The purpose of this section is to complement the DIC and the step-by-step guide with a concrete recommendation of how a dashboard can be technically implemented.

4.1. Introduction

4.1.1. What is R Shiny?

[R](#) is a scripting language and analysis software used globally by researchers and data scientists for statistical computing and data analysis. It is open source and proposes a large set of libraries to achieve a range of analysis, data manipulation and visualisation.

[Shiny](#) is a library for R, allowing a developer to create a dashboard with interactive graphs, by writing R code only. No knowledge of website development languages (HTML, CSS and JS) is required. If the developer has knowledge of these basic web development languages, it is possible to integrate custom scripts and stylesheets to a Shiny dashboard to create a more complex and customisable website.

4.1.2. Implementation Requirements

Technical skills:

- Fundamental:
 - Knowledge of R
- Beneficial:
 - Understanding of basic web languages and website structure
 - Knowledge of HTML and CSS for visual design
 - Knowledge of JS for more advanced custom UI features

Infrastructure:

- Any computer on which R can be installed
- A version control workflow (e.g., git) is very helpful and highly recommended, especially for collaborative projects

4.1.3. Strengths and Weaknesses

Strengths:

- A single person with some R knowledge can easily create a dashboard from scratch
- Seamless integration to the data flow (data cleaning, manipulation, analyses, visualisation)
- Access to the whole set of R libraries for data manipulation, analysis and visualisation
- Very modular - possibility to add blocks of text or graphs in almost any layout you want.
- Good visual theming options
- Possibility to integrate CSS, JS, custom HTML templates, CSS pre-processors, etc...

Weaknesses:

- The code behind complex dashboards can become quite intricate
- Advanced customisation of visual design and page layout requires good knowledge of HTML and CSS

4.2. Getting Started

4.2.1. Resources and Learning Material

It is possible to start making Shiny dashboard with entry- to intermediate-level R skills.

The [2.5H video tutorial](#) on R Shiny's main page is a very good start and will take you through the structure of Shiny apps, the basics of layout and all reactivity functions.

To go further, the [Articles page](#) on R Shiny's main page has detailed information on performance optimisation, UI and integration of HTML, CSS and JS.

Eventually, making better dashboards will mean improving the delivery of information to the user through clearer content, better content flow and better UI and UX design.

5. Practical Examples of Dashboards and Tools

In the DIC: <https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/docs/examples/>

This section is an inventory of planned or existing interactive dashboards and tools developed by member institutes of the MATRIX project. The purpose is both to add more value to the DIC by exemplifying the information with real-world examples, and to spread the word about the tools to potentially interested users.

A detailed description of the dashboards and tools developed, along with links and figures, is presented in MATRIX deliverable D-WP6.2.

6. Resources

In the DIC: <https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/docs/resources/>

This section provides information on relevant presentations that have been held project, their topics and the presenters along with a download link. This could be a useful source of information for those who want to find out more about the topics covered and who may want to reach out to the presenters for further information.

The presentations listed are found in Table 1.

Table 1. A list of presentations held within WP6 which may be of interest for OHS dashboard developers.

Presenter	Topic	Download link
Wiktor Gustafsson (SVA)	Presentation of Swedish annual disease surveillance report workflow and dashboards	https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/presentations/20220628_monthly_meeting_presentation.pdf
Emily Dibba White (SSI)	The work behind the Danish COVID-19 dashboard	https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/presentations/Dashboards_connecting_people_2022.04.19.pdf
Adriano Di Pasquale (IZS)	The COHESIVE Information System	https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/presentations/20220224_cohesive-system.pdf
Clémence Koren (FHI/NIPH)	Designing a One Health website - Tips for user-friendliness and visual appeal	https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/presentations/2021_09_23_MATRIX_presentation_userfriendliness_Clemence_Koren.pdf
Taras Günther, Matthias Filter (BfR)	Making linked data accessible for One Health Surveillance with the One Health Linked Data Toolbox	https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/presentations/MATRIX_The-OH-EJP-LOD-Toolbox_TG_230621.pdf
Gry Grøneng, Richard White (FHI/NIPH)	Presentation of Norwegian One Health website Sykdomspulsen	https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/presentations/MatrixWP6_25032021.pdf

In this section we also list external resources of relevance to the DIC and the OHEJP.

7. Contact

In the DIC: <https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/docs/contact/>

This section is important for the people who seek more information about dashboard development or who have specific problems or questions which they need further help with. In this section in the DIC, we list a number of people as representatives of their country and institute, or who have specific expertise in a topic relevant to OHS or dashboard development, along with their email addresses. This is useful for helping persons who may have specific questions, but also to promote the people who have contributed to and stand behind the DIC and the dashboards presented within.

Conclusion and further directions

The DIC is a useful guide and source of information for people who are planning to develop, are developing or have already developed a dashboard, particularly for the purposes of OHS. Through providing external resources and contact information, the DIC also promotes collaboration and network building, and helps users find the right people to contact for the information they need.

The work within WP6 and with the DIC has added significant value to the group as a whole, creating connections between institutes that are working on similar One Health tasks and opening opportunities for new collaboration.

We aim for the DIC to be sustained beyond the time scope of the OHEJP project, as it is expected to remain a useful resource both for OHEJP members and others for several coming years. To achieve this, we aim to ensure that the content remains up-to-date and relevant as the field of One Health Surveillance Dashboards changes and evolves.